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MATHEMATICAL APPARATUS FOR CALCULATING A CYLINDRICAL PERMANENT MAGNET MAGNETIZED ALONG THE LENGTH BASED ON USECASE

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Annotation: The work presents the mathematical apparatus for analytical calculation of the magnetic parameters of the working points and the magnetic field outside the magnetic pole of a cylindrical permanent magnet, magnetized separately in length and according to the application of the magnetic system, as well as of the dimensions of the permanent magnet. New expressions have been introduced into the calculation theory. The graphical connection of magnetic field parameters, data from the analytical and experimental studies, interpretations, and conclusions are presented.

Keywords: permanent magnet, magnetic system, working point, induction

Introduction.

The purposes of using a permanent magnet (PM) are to ensure the needed magnitude of the magnetic field in an open-air location outside of the magnet (open magnetic system (Fig. 1a) or in point *a* of the working gap of the system with a magnetic wire (a semi-closed PM system) (Fig. 1b) or in a close magnetic system (Fig. 1c).

Figure 1 – PM application options

For the calculation of the magnetic parameters of the PM there exist numerous published works [1÷7] mainly with a graph-theoretical. These works do not always provide sufficient magnetic parameters or only partially provide the necessary ones, as mentioned in works [8, 9]. The Internet resources [10÷14] also offer the possibility to calculate certain magnetic parameters of PM using appropriate software.

The mathematical formulations used in this work ensure a complete and consistent calculation of the magnetic parameters and dimensions of PM according to various application models.

Proposed tasks.

1. To develop a mathematical apparatus for a magnetic system magnetized separately along the length of a cylindrical PM:
 - magnetic parameters of working points and dimensions,
 - magnetic induction along the length axis outside the magnet.
2. To prove the accuracy and practical applicability of the use of mathematical apparatus by practical research.

The solution to the problem.

To make the work more descriptive, the graph-analytical and analytical methods of the solutions and their mutual connection is presented.

The following permissions are made: the PM material is homogeneous, it is magnetized in a homogeneous magnetic field with the corresponding axis until saturation, and stabilization is applied.

In case of each of the three application cases of the PM the calculation starts at evaluating the magnetic parameters of the working points of the PM.

1. In the mathematical apparatus, the initial data is the following parameters

- the brand of the PM;
- the length of the PM, ℓ_{PM} , *mm*;
- the diameter of the PM, d_{PM} , *mm*;
- distance to point *a* from the pole, *x*, *mm* (Fig. 2).

Figure 2 – Polarization and dimensional designations of PM

2. Referencing the directory, the following parameters of the PM material are registered:

- the coercive force by induction, H_{cB} , *A/m*;
- the residual induction, B_r , *T*;
- the maximum energy product, $(BH)_m$, *J/m³*.

3. The characteristics of B(-H) PM are plotted on the plane of the coordinate axis in accordance with the following known expression (Fig. 3)

$$B_i = B_r \frac{H_{cB} - H_i}{H_{cB} - \gamma_c H_i}, \quad (1)$$

where the values of H_i are picked from the range 0 to H_{cB} , a γ_c the convexity coefficient of the material PM, the value of which is within $0 < \gamma_c < 1$ and is determined as follows

$$\gamma_c = 2 \sqrt{\frac{H_{cB} B_r}{(BH)_m} - \frac{H_{cB} B_r}{(BH)_m}}. \quad (2)$$

Figure 3 – B(-H) characteristic and working points of the PM

4. The value of the permeability coefficient m_p of the PM form is determined [8, 9].

For a cylindrical PM with a $\frac{d_{PM}}{\ell_{PM}}$ ratio of the 0,1÷10 interval (except when $\frac{d_{PM}}{\ell_{PM}} = 1$), it is suggested to use the following expression

$$m_p = 2,46 \left(\frac{d_{PM}}{\ell_{PM}} \right)^{-1,32}. \quad (3)$$

$$\text{When } \frac{d_{PM}}{\ell_{PM}} = 1, m_p = 3. \quad (4)$$

5. The parameters of the PM in the cross section of the neutral 00 are determined by the famous expressions (Fig. 3).

Magnetic induction

$$B_0 = \frac{k_0 - \sqrt{k_0^2 - 4\mu_0 \gamma_c m_p H_{cb} B_r}}{2\gamma_c}, \quad (5)$$

where $k_0 = (B_r + \mu_0 m_p H_{cb})$, $\mu_0 = 4\pi 10^{-7} \text{Hn/m}$.

Magnetic field voltage

$$H_0 = \frac{B_0}{\mu_0 m_p}, \text{ or } H_0 = H_{cb} \frac{B_0 - B_r}{\gamma_c B_0 - B_r}. \quad (6)$$

Graphically, the values of B_0 and H_0 are determined using α_0 angle.

$$\alpha_0 = \arctg \mu_0 m_p k_m = \frac{B_0}{H_0} k_m, \quad (7)$$

where k_m is the scale factor according to the constructed graph $k_m = \frac{m_H}{m_B} \left[\frac{A/m}{T} \right]$.

6. Calculation of magnetic induction at the N PM pole for option Figure 1a

$$B_N = (\mu_0 H_0 + B_0) \frac{\ell_{PM}}{\sqrt{4\ell_{PM}^2 + d_{PM}^2}} \tag{8}$$

7. The magnetic induction of scattering is determined

$$B_\sigma = B_0 - B_N \tag{9}$$

8. The scattering coefficient by magnetic induction is determined

$$k_\sigma = \frac{B_0}{B_N} \tag{10}$$

9. The magnetic conductivity of PM is determined

$$\Lambda_0 = \frac{B_0 S_{PM}}{H_0 \ell_{PM}} = \text{tg} \alpha_0 \frac{S_{PM}}{\ell_{PM} k_m} \tag{11}$$

where S_{PM} is the area of PM's transverse cross-section $S_{PM} = \pi d_{PM}^2 / 4$.

10. The magnetic conductivity PM along the pole N is determined

$$\Lambda_N = \frac{B_N S_{PM}}{H_0 \ell_{PM}} = \text{tg} \alpha_N \frac{S_{PM}}{\ell_{PM} k_m} \tag{12}$$

where

$$\alpha_N = \text{arctg} \frac{B_N}{H_0} k_m = \text{arctg} \Lambda_N \frac{\ell_{PM}}{S_{PM}} k_m \tag{13}$$

11. Magnetic conductivity due to scattering induction

$$\Lambda_\sigma = \frac{B_0 S_{PM}}{H_0 \ell_{PM}} = \text{tg} \alpha_\sigma \frac{S_{PM}}{\ell_{PM} k_m} \tag{14}$$

$$\text{where } \alpha_\sigma = \alpha_0 - \alpha_N \tag{15}$$

12. The total magnetic conductivity of the PM is determined

$$\Lambda_\Sigma \Lambda_\Sigma = \Lambda_N + \Lambda_\sigma \tag{16}$$

Figure 3 shows the PM characteristic, the location of the working points (A_0, H_0) , (A_N, H_0) and the corresponding angles.

13. The magnitude of the induction B_a at point a at a distance x from the pole in variant Figure 1a

$$B_a = k_M k_{PM} \tag{17}$$

where the value of k_M is determined by the magnetic parameters of the PM

$$k_M = \frac{1}{2} (\mu_0 H_0 + B_N) \tag{18}$$

and the value of k_{PM} - by the geometric values of the PM and the value of x

$$k_{PM} = 2 \left[\frac{\ell_{PM+x}}{\sqrt{4(\ell_{PM+x})^2 + d_{PM}^2}} - \frac{x}{\sqrt{4x^2 + d_{PM}^2}} \right]. \quad (19)$$

The generalized expression for determining the value of the function $B_a = f(x)$ is given by

$$B_a = (\mu_0 H_0 + B_N) \left[\frac{\ell_{PM+x}}{\sqrt{4(\ell_{PM+x})^2 + d_{PM}^2}} - \frac{x}{\sqrt{4x^2 + d_{PM}^2}} \right]. \quad (20)$$

14. Expressions of dimensions PM by magnetic parameters:

$$d_{PM} = \frac{\ell_{PM}}{B_N} \sqrt{(\mu_0 H_0 + B_0)^2 - 4B_N^2}, \quad (21)$$

$$\ell_{PM} = \frac{B_N d_{PM}}{\sqrt{(\mu_0 H_0 + B_0)^2 - 4B_N^2}}. \quad (22)$$

15. After importing the PM into the magnetic system (Figure 1b) the working points A0 and AN of the PM are moved by the return direction correspondingly to the positions A'0 and A'N [(H'0, B'0) and (H'0, B'N), Figure 3] resulting in increase of the Λ_s conductivity of the PM's magnetic system.

The determination of the positions of A'0 and A'N points graphically are done by well-known expressions of the return coefficient and the angles,

$$\rho_r = \frac{B_r}{H_{CB}} (1 - \gamma_c), \quad (23)$$

$$\beta_r = \arctg \rho_r k_m, \quad (24)$$

$$\alpha'_0 = \arctg \Lambda_s \frac{\ell_{PM}}{S_{PM}} k_m. \quad (25)$$

The graphic design is known from the literature and is depicted in Figure 3.

The coordinates of point A'0 are determined by the following expression,

$$H'_0 = \frac{B_0 H_{cf}}{B_0 - k_1 (H_0 - H_{cf})}, \quad (26)$$

$$B'_0 = k_1 H'_0, \quad (27)$$

where H_{cf} fictitious coercive force $H_{cf} = \frac{B_0}{\rho_r} + H_0$, $k_1 = \frac{\ell_{PM}}{S_{PM}} \Lambda_s$.

If the magnetic conductivity of the scattering fluxes remains unchanged then

$$B'_N = B'_0 - B_\sigma. \quad (28)$$

16. In the case of the magnetic system given in Figure 1b, to determine the other dimensions H_0 , B_0 and B_N in the given expressions are substituted by H'_0 , B'_0 and B'_N .

17. In the close magnetic system (Fig. 1c) the inductions B'_0 and B'_N are determined as follows (if the magnetic loss in the magnetic wire is ignored, and the conductivity of scattering fluxes remains unchanged):

$$B'_0 = H'_0 \rho_r + B'_0, \tag{29}$$

$$B'_N = B'_0 - B_\sigma. \tag{30}$$

Researched PM, tools and preparation.

The following cylindrical PM were selected for the study. 1). brand N35, sizes $\ell_{PM}=19,5mm$, $d_{PM}=19,5mm$; 2). brand N38, sizes $\ell_{PM}=10mm$, $d_{PM}=30mm$; 3). brand N52, sizes $\ell_{PM}=30mm$, $d_{PM}=50mm$.

Magnetic induction in the pole of the PM and with different values of x was measured using a BST-600 teslameter.

The different values of x are provided by the use of non-ferromagnetic pads, the width of which was measured using digital calipers of the HARDENED brand.

The difference of magnetic potential between the poles N-S of the PM has been measured using magnetic potentiometer (Rogovsky belt) the average diameter of which was around $d_b=6,8mm$. As a measuring device, a digital microwebermeter F5050 was used. The average value of coefficient magnetic potentiometer – measuring device was $6,93 \cdot 10^6$.

Research results.

For the calculation, out of many sources [15] was selected for recording the data of the PM by brand.

A. 1). The reference source provides the following parameters: $H_{cB}=(836 \div 891) \cdot 10^3 A/m$, $B_r=(1,17 \div 1,22)T$, $(BH)_m=(263 \div 279) \cdot 10^3 J/m^3$.

The following parameters are selected for the calculation: $H_{cB}=836 \cdot 10^3 A/m$, $B_r=1,17T$, $(BH)_m=263 \cdot 10^3 J/m^3$.

According to the presented mathematical apparatus for calculation, the following results were obtained: $B_0=0,88T$, $H_0=233 \cdot 10^3 A/m$, $B_N^c=0,524T$, $B_\sigma=0,356T$, $k_\sigma = 1,68$, $k_M^c=0,408$.

The average value of induction measured at the N poles of 12 PMs was $B_{Nav}^m=0,352T$.

The relative error for B_N was about $\varepsilon = (B_N^c - B_{Nav}^m)100 / B_{Nav}^m = 49 \%$.

To study $B_a(x)$ for the selected PM $B_N^m=0,34T$.

The calculated $B_a^c(x)$ and the measured $B_a^m(x)$ magnetic inductions and the values of their relative deviation δ by % based on the brand of the PM are given in the table, where $\delta=|(B_a^c - B_a^m)|100/ B_a^m$.

Based on the measured B_a^m the average $k_{Mav}^m=0,38$.

The relative deviation between computational k_M^c and experimental k_{Mav}^m was about 7,4 %.

2.) The reference source provides the following parameters: $H_{CB}=(836\div 891)\cdot 10^3 A/m$, $B_r=(1,22\div 1,26)T$, $(BH)_m=(279\div 302)\cdot 10^3 J/m^3$.

The following parameters are selected for the calculation: $H_{CB}=836\cdot 10^3 A/m$, $B_r=1,22T$, $(BH)_m=279\cdot 10^3 J/m^3$.

According to the presented mathematical apparatus for calculation, the following results were obtained: $B_0=0,422T$, $H_0=582\cdot 10^3 A/m$, $B_N^c=0,32T$, $B_\sigma=0,102T$, $k_\sigma=1,32$, $k_M^c=0,525$.

The average value of induction measured in the N poles of 12 PMs was $B_{Nav}^m=0,295T$.

The relative error for B_N was about $\varepsilon=8,5\%$.

To study $B_a(x)$ for the selected PM $B_N^m=0,292T$.

Based on the measured B_a^m the average $k_{Mav}^m=0,517$.

The relative deviation between computational k_M^c and experimental k_{Mav}^m was about 1,5 %.

3.) The reference source provides the following parameters: $H_{CB}=(860\div 995)\cdot 10^3 A/m$, $B_r=(1,42\div 1,47)T$, $(BH)_m=(380\div 422)\cdot 10^3 J/m^3$.

The following parameters are selected for the calculation: $H_{CB}=860\cdot 10^3 A/m$, $B_r=1,42T$, $(BH)_m=380\cdot 10^3 J/m^3$.

According to the presented mathematical apparatus for calculation, the following results were obtained: $B_0=0,775T$, $H_0=490\cdot 10^3 A/m$, $B_N^c=0,534T$, $B_\sigma=0,241T$, $k_\sigma=1,32$, $k_M^c=0,575$.

The average value of induction measured in the N poles of 10 PMs was $B_{Nav}^m=0,425T$.

The relative deviation for B_N was about $\varepsilon=26\%$.

To study $B_a(x)$ for the selected PM $B_N^m=0,42T$.

Based on the measured B_a^m the average $k_{Mav}^m=0,539$.

The relative deviation between computational k_M^c and experimental k_{Mav}^m was around 6,7 %.

Table 1 – Research results

PM	X, mm	4,83	9,75	14,85	19,85	24,79	29,73	34,69	39,75	44,73	50,20
1).	B_N^c, T	0,197	0,0863	0,0514	0,0298	0,0187	0,0125	0,0087	0,0063	0,0047	0,0035
	B_N^m, T	0,1806	0,0913	0,0484	0,0284	0,0176	0,0118	0,082	0,0058	0,0043	0,0034
	$\delta, \%$	9,1	5,5	6,2	4,9	6,2	5,9	6,1	8,6	9,3	2,9
2).	B_N^c, T	0,208	0,132	0,0802	0,0502	0,033	0,0228	0,0158	0,0114	0,0086	0,0065
	B_N^m, T	0,209	0,130	0,0794	0,0496	0,0324	0,0222	0,0157	0,0112	0,0084	0,0064
	$\delta, \%$	0,5	1,5	1,0	1,2	1,8	1,8	0,6	1,8	2,4	1,6
3).	B_N^c, T	0,357	0,277	0,208	0,156	0,1180	0,0901	0,0698	0,0543	0,0433	0,0318
	B_N^m, T	0,3346	0,2592	0,1952	0,1465	0,1105	0,0844	0,0656	0,0513	0,0407	0,0328
	$\delta, \%$	6,7	6,5	6,9	6,4	6,5	6,7	6,4	5,8	6,4	3,0

B. By the version of Figure 1a the research of the voltage of the magnetic field between the poles N-S of the PM.

After registering the difference between the magnetic potentials of the poles N-S and corresponding calculations the resulted values of magnetic voltage H_{NS} and the ratio $k_d=d_{PM}/d_b$ correspondingly were 1). $227,7 \cdot 10^3 A/m$, $k_d=2,9$, 2). $567,1 \cdot 10^3 A/m$, $k_d=4,4$, 3). $448,1 \cdot 10^3 A/m$, $k_d=7,5$.

The computational values of H_0 in the PMs correspondingly were 1). $H_0=232 \cdot 10^3 A/m$, 2). $H_0=582 \cdot 10^3 A/m$, 3). $H_0=490 \cdot 10^3 A/m$.

The relative deviations of computational and experimental results were 1). 1,9 %, 2). 2,6 % 3). 9,3 %.

Conclusion.

1. The big difference between computational and experimental results of B_N (49 %) can be interpreted by.

a) by the choice of the value of the quantities given by the difference and range of the reference data of the PM.

b) during the measurements, it was found that the B_N has different values at different points on the surface of the N pole of the PM, and the induction at some points is greater than that of the centroid of the pole surface.

c) the inhomogeneity of the magnetic field at the N pole has slight effect on the value of k_M (7,4 %).

2. The calculated $B_a(x)$ results of different brands and sizes of PMs can be said to represent the experimental ones quite well, as the values of δ do not exceed 9.3 %.

3. The mathematical calculation apparatus is simple and accessible from the point of view of application in the engineering and scientific research processes of research and improvement of magnetic parameters, dimensions, magnetic field, dimensions of the magnetic system structure and PM.

Gratitude

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